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Moving Toward Sustainable Aquaculture for Rural Sustainability and Development in Kenya. A Case of Vihiga County

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ABSTRACT

Kenya has a tremendous great potential for growth in the aquaculture sector. To attain the sustainable development goal of zero hunger, the government is needed to encourage fish culture among the rural communities. The study's objective is to investigate the elements that affect the sustainable development of fresh water Aquaculture in Kenya a Vihiga County case. The purpose of the research is to determine how production characteristics and extension affect the long-term sustainability of freshwater aquaculture and how socioeconomic factors, training, and Extension services influence the long-term sustainability of fresh water aquaculture. The research design was descriptive. 110 fish farmers were the study's target set of respondents. The study's sample size was 96 respondents, who were identified by Krejcie and Morgan's table. The information was collected via a questionnaire, and descriptive statistics were used in an excel spreadsheet using a statistical tool for social sciences to analyze the information. Tables, graphs, and pie charts were used to present the findings. Based on the survey, the majority of respondents (55) owned 1 or 2 ponds, and 92.3% had never closed a pond. Based on the research, 76.9% of respondents culture tilapia in their farm. The majority of 47.4% and 44.9% of fingerlings came from Neighbours and government farms, respectively. The study also revealed that 61.5% of respondents utilize earthen ponds with river water as their main source of water. 42.3% of respondents, in accordance with the report, manage the parameters and water level of their ponds daily. The study also showed that whereas 29.6% of respondents had experienced bacterial infections in their fish farm, 46.2% of respondents had never experienced fish diseases. By 67.9%, birds were the primary fish predators. 88.7% of respondents said they have attended aquaculture training. The study's main conclusion is that a broad range of variables affect the sustainable development of fresh water. The study suggests that the county government of Vihiga should create distinct marketing strategies for farmed fish. For those actively promoting the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in Kenya, the research is essential.

1.0. Introduction

The ability to meet immediate needs without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to satisfy their own needs is termed as sustainability (United Nations Assembly report, 2013). In order to improve food production through the aquaculture sector, sustainability is crucial. Three main facets of sustainability have a direct impact on the expansion of aquaculture globally. These aspects include social, environmental, and economic elements. Sustainability has been a concern in the

development of aquaculture mostly in number of developing countries, notably Kenya. There are various multiple kinds of sustainability issues, such as market sustainability, social sustainability, and biodiversity conservation that greatly impact on aquaculture. Moccia and Hynes (1998) include societal strife, environmental issues, market instability, and global competition for the fish market as challenges for aquaculture sustainability. Market stability, requirements for food safety and standards, and consumer confidence in cultured fish as opposed to capture fisheries are all factors that affect aquaculture sustainability.

Environmental management is the most critical issue in regards to the treatment of solid waste and the discharge of fish farm effluent into an aquatic ecosystem (Bureau ,2006). The pressure on environmental issues has resulted in a decrease in aquaculture growth, which has an effect on the sector's sustainability. There are currently limited safety standards that regulate how aquaculture impacts the environment (Moccia and Bevan, 2000). This demonstrates that aquaculture's sustainability concerns are compromised, and environmental laws specially tailored for the industry are needed to promote its sustained development. Sustainability is viewed as a requirement of our generation, (World Bank ,1994).To manage the resource base such that the average quality of life we guarantee for ourselves might potentially be shared by all future generations. Development and safeguarding of aquaculture and fisheries resources could result from it.As the demand for global capture fisheries reaches its maximum level, the(FAO ,2015) anticipates that by 2030, the aquaculture sector will be the main source of both fresh water and seafood. However, in order for aquaculture systems employed for fish production to be truly sustainable, the systems must be environmentally sound, with no loss of biodiversity or water pollution (Helfrich (2009) who reviewed that pollutants such household wastes, industrial wastes, pesticides, and herbicides used in agriculture are linked to fish kills caused by pollution in ponds. The system should also be financially sustainable, with aquaculture projects requiring better long-term market strategies in order to achieve profitability. Aquaculture must also positively contribute to the well-being of the society on a public scale. According to FAO (2015), sustainable aquaculture is a flexible approach where the system's effectiveness varies depending on the species being raised, the technology being used, and the location of the culture system. Aquaculture, according to Ahmed (2002), is the practice of raising fish, algae, crustaceans, mollusks, and aquatic plants under confined water body.With a 9.9% growth in animal farming since 2000, aquaculture is the protein production system that is growing the fastest globally (FAO, 2018). This illustrates that aquaculture can feed a large number of individuals globally while also earning a living for the vast majority of farmers. Since 2000, the production of aquaculture globally has increased, reaching its peak in 2016. (FAO 2018).Based upon those findings, the aquaculture sector needs to grow sustainably in order to increase productivity. The global supply of fish for human consumption has increased attributable to aquaculture.

Due to a substantial fall in production of fresh water fish species from both capture fisheries and aquaculture, there has been an upsurge in global demand for fish (FAO, 2018).The basis of this study was whether sustainable aquaculture production methods must be established to supplement the world decline in fish production. Under the Economic Stimulus Program (ESP), the Kenyan government has been able to support fish farming in 140 constituencies across the country. Each of Kenya's 140 constituencies received 200 fish ponds, 25 kg of fertilizer, 1000 Tilapia fingerlings, and 5 bags of 50 kg fish feeds as grants to farmers between 2009to 2013 (MOFD ,2013).This has allowed aquaculture develop across the vast majority of the Counties notably Vihiga County. In the 2011–2012 financial year, this Programme initiated its second phase, including the enrollment of an additional 20 constituencies. Furthermore, each of the 140 constituencies received another 100 fish ponds, totaling 300 fish ponds for the new constituencies. As a result, approximately 50,000 ponds were constructed in Kenya at a cost of 18 million US dollars (MOFD, 2012).

Despite government initiatives to promote the aquaculture industry, the right species to be cultured, and prolific tilapia breeding in ponds, the production of fresh water fish through aquaculture is still low in Kenya. The findings of this research would be leveraged to improve the status of the aquaculture industry that is currently overseen through county governments and assure that the fish farming techniques utilized in Kenya are sustainable. The findings will aid the department of fisheries and the blue economy and County Government of Vihiga to develop policies on how to improve fresh water fish farming throughout county through the department of fisheries at the county government level. Other scholars and researchers engaged in the fields of aquaculture and food security will find the research beneficial as supplementary original source for their projects and future research. The aim of the study was to investigate production factors influencing sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in Vihiga County. Whose specific objectives were, to examine how Production/ecological factors influence sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in the five sub counties in Vihiga County, to investigate the influence of social- economic factors, Training and Extension on sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in the two sub counties in Vihiga County.

2.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Research Design

In this study, a descriptive research design was employed. Estimating the occurrence frequency between the study's variables is the focus of descriptive design (Bryman and Bell, 2003). In contrast to quantitative techniques, descriptive research design is the most effective approach for investigating the factors influencing the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in Vihiga County. The study design is deemed appropriate since it can define variables without altering variables. 110 respondents who were active fish farmers with two or more ponds and who had been purposively sampled from 5 sub-counties comprised the study's target population. Fish farmers that made up the target group for this study's sample size totaled 110. Respondents were chosen using approaches for purposeful sampling. The respondents were divided into groups based on which sub county they reside in (Sabatia, Lunda, Vihiga Sub County or Emuhaya Sub County).

The researcher then calculated the actual sample size for each group of responders using Krejcie and Morgan Table (Krejcie and Morgan 1970). The technique enables the researcher to adopt cases that are directly related to the objectives of the study. The sample size for this study based on Krejcie and Morgan table is obtained as 96 respondents.

2.2. Research Instruments and procedures

Data was collected through a questionnaire. This is due to the simplicity with which surveys can be distributed to respondents who are dispersed across a wide geographic area. Both open-ended and closed-ended questions were contained in the questionnaire's content. The use of open-ended questions, nevertheless, enables respondents to give a comprehensive response without feeling confined from disclosing specific information. Based on the objectives of the study, the questionnaires were divided into two sections. But the aim of the questionnaire's first section was to learn more about the respondents' background. The researcher first received a study authorization from Kenya's National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI) to carry out research in Kenya to proceeding to collect data from the field. The surveys were then distributed along with participant consent forms. Participants were given participant debriefing forms to fill out after receiving the questionnaire so they may expound on their opinions of the research. The School of Biology at the University of St. Andrews' ethical committee and the research supervisor had all been given access to research instrument (the questionnaire) for validation in order to determine its validity and make sure that it contains all the elements and concepts necessary for the study in accordance with the research objectives.

In accordance with the study's aims, the collected data was coded and analyzed using SPSS and an Excel spreadsheet. Pie charts, frequency distributions, tabulation graphs, and percentages were used to display the results of the descriptive statistics calculation. The content analysis method was used to examine the qualitative data from the open-ended questionnaire.

3.0. Results

The findings of the study is presented based on the objectives of the study and research question.

3.1. Production & ecological factors' influence on the sustainability of freshwater aquaculture.

Fish species raised, the number of ponds, sources of fingerlings, water sources, the nature of the ponds, water pollution, fish predators, diseases, the type of fish feeds used, and routine farm husbandry management were all examined for their effects on the sustainability of fresh water aquaculture. Ponds owned by farmers and those that have been abandoned in regard to production and sustainability. 55% of the respondents owned between one and two ponds on their farms, according to the findings. 16% farmers with three to four ponds. And 5% farmers and 2% farmers had 5 to 6 ponds and 7 and above ponds respectively in their farm. In terms of ponds shut down, a significant portion of respondents—72 (92.3%)—had no ponds shut down at all during production. This was followed by 5 (6.4%) of the respondents who had one pond shut down. Only one (1.3%) fish farmer has shut down two ponds.

Figure 3.1: Respondents by number of ponds closed

Respondents by Number of closed ponds			
Number of ponds	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
0	72	92.3	92.3
1	5	6.4	98.7
2	1	1.3	100.0
Total	78	100.0	

Additionally, the respondents had to identify the major fish species they produce on their farm and describe how sustainable those species are. The results thus indicate that the majority of respondents, 60 (76.9%), only stocked tilapia in their fish farm. Only 3 (3.8%) of the respondents stocked African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) in their farm, despite the fact that that 15 (19.2%) of respondents had mixed species of catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) stocked. This is because African catfish has a low market demand in the western part of Kenya.

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Figure 3.2. Fish species culture

Regarding the origin of fingerlings and the degree of sustainability and dependability needed for the development of fresh water aquaculture. The finding indicate that majority of fish farmers 37(47.4%) and 35 (44.9%) obtained fingerlings from Neighbours farm and Government hatchery which is Mwitoko aquaculture training center respectively. This shows that for the sustainability of their fish farms, farmers primarily depend on other farmers with high-quality fingerlings and from County government farms. Only 6 respondents (7.7%) stated that “they purchased their fingerlings from private hatcheries. This occurs because these private hatcheries' fingerlings are of poor quality and the source is unpredictable (Mbugua, 2008).

Regarding fingerling reliability, the majority of the 70 farmers who responded (89.7%) said that their fingerling source is reliable and sustainable for the development of aquaculture in the area. Only 8 respondents (10.3%) said their supplier is unreliable and unsustainable, most probably because they obtain their fingerling from private hatcheries without a clear growth strategy. This illustrates as reviewed by Johnson, (2013) that any fish farmer should consider sustainability and reliability while planning for the long-term growth of fresh water aquaculture.

On the nature of fish ponds, the results indicate that 77 (98.7%) of the respondents constructed earthen ponds, which represents the majority of the respondents. But only 1 (1.3%) of the participants had a liner pond. The reason for this is because constructing earthen ponds is easier and cheaper than constructing liner or concrete ponds. Addressing the fish farm's water source and sustainability, The findings revealed that the majority of respondents—48 (61.5%)—get their pond water from streams, while 22 (28.2%) received it from springs.

According to Nyandat, & Owiti (2013), In Vihiga County, river and streams are the primary sources of water for aquaculture. However, for the practice of aquaculture, 7 (9%) respondents used well water, while 1 (1.3%) respondents use water collected from roofs.

According to farmers, Vihiga County's rivers are the most reliable source of water for aquaculture. This is caused by the county's varied topography and the abundance of rivers and streams.

The respondents were also required in their own viewpoint to evaluate whether the source of water for aquaculture use is sustainable for Aquaculture. The finding showed that majority of the respondents 72 (92.3%) accepted that the source was sustainable. Only 6 (7.7%) respondents disagreed. Based on famers opinion on sustainability River water and spring water are most sustainable source of water for Aquaculture in Vihiga County.

On Pond Water Level Maintenance and Water Quality Parameter Monitoring. The respondents were asked how often they monitor water parameters such temperature, turbidity, dissolved oxygen level (DO), ammonia level, and pH as well as how frequently they maintain pond water levels. According to the results, 42.3% of respondents of the majority maintained the water level in their ponds at the same level each day. While 34.6% kept the water level the same weekly basis.20.5% of respondents claimed they monitor their pond's water level once each month, According to Ngugi, *etal* (2007) Good husbandry in an aquaculture system is characteristic of sustainable aquaculture production.

Regarding the effects of water pollution, disease, and fish predator nature on the sustainability of aquaculture. The results indicate that 67.9% of respondents said that birds are their main fish predators, while 24.4% claimed snakes were predators in their farm. 1.3% and 6.4% of the respondents, respectively, reported encounters with river otters and other creatures, especially humans and frogs. According to other related studies, the main predators affecting the viability of aquaculture in Kenya are birds and snakes (Mbugua, 2008). Fish farming is now being threatened by humans and frogs as predators.

The majority of the respondents (46.2%) who were classified as others specifically stated that they had not encountered any fish illnesses or diseases when questioned about the kinds of fish diseases experienced in the farm, according to survey. Other respondents, however, reported that they had experienced fish stress due to “low levels of oxygen in their ponds, especially nighttime and early in the day. Furthermore, bacterial infections of the fish had only been experienced among 29.6% of the respondents. Similarly, among their fish stock, 15.4% and 11.5% of respondents reported pathogens and viral diseases, respectively. The most of vihiga fish farmers have not experienced any serious fish diseases. Another factor influencing fish culture is water pollution.

The respondents had to describe a type of water pollution that was limiting aquaculture. This shows that most fish farmers do not comply to the required feeding ratios and rates for the sustainable use of fish feeds, that causes water pollution. This was followed by domestic garbage, which was mentioned by 21 (26.9%) of the respondents, pesticides and herbicides used on agricultural farms, and industrial discharge, which was mentioned by 13 (16.7%) of the respondents and 11 (14.1% of the respondents, respectively.

Aquaculture production and sustainability are directly impacted by the fish diets that are used. (Miles, & Chapman, 2015). The type of fish feed that the respondents use to feed their fish in their ponds was a prerequisite of the survey. Identify the feeds' sustainability for aquaculture production as well.

The results revealed that the majority of fish farmers (82.1%) use commercial fish feeds. Because the majority of fish farmers can afford commercial feeds, which are easily accessible in the local market.

However, 9% of the respondents feed their fish with local feeds and nutrients from ponds. 7.7% of the respondents said that some farmers utilize homemade feeds. 1.3% of respondents reported using sweet potato-based feed from others. The respondents were asked whether the feed they are using is sustainable in fish production in order to boost on the sustainable production of fresh water aquaculture. The findings indicate that the majority of respondents, or 87.2%, concurred that the feed is sustainable in the

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3.2. Influence of socioeconomic factors, training, and Extension services on the long-term sustainability of fresh water aquaculture

The participants were asked to provide data about the funding they used to establish and operate their fish farming projects. Further, they had to explain whether their source of funding was long-term enough to encourage the expansion of freshwater aquaculture in Vihiga County. The findings showed that the majority of respondents (51.3%) established and invested in fish farming projects through their savings and investments. According to 41.5% of respondents, the government provided significant support to fish farmers to start their fish farming business through the department of fisheries and county governments.

7.7% of the respondents stated that some farmers got funding from Sacco loans. According to these findings, the primary sources of funding for fish farming enterprises in Vihiga County are individual savings and government aid.

Figure 3.3. Sources of funding for starting and operating fish farm project

On the systems of land tenure and ownership for aquaculture operations and sustainability. Based on the findings, 13 (16.7%) of the respondents utilized freehold land for aquaculture, while 50 (64.1% of the respondents) used family land. Only 9 (11.5%) of respondents lease land, but 6 (7.7%) own their own land. Following these data, family and freehold land in Vihiga County are where the preponderance of aquaculture activities are undertaken. Land is leased by very few farmers for aquaculture systems.

According to Chaudhuri (2008) the tenure system for land ownership, family land is considered more sustainable than other types of property ownership for any aquaculture production systems. According to the study's findings, the majority of 49 respondents (62.8%) believed that the land ownership tenure structure in existence has a Very High influence on the long-term sustainability of freshwater aquaculture.

On labour availability and sustainability ,59 (75.6%) of respondents reported they totally depend on employed staff to provide labour in their fish farm, which is the major source of labour for fish farming and its sustainability in the growth of fresh water aquaculture. However, 19 (24.4%) of the activities required family labour, implying that contracting labour is more sustainable for aquaculture practice. The finding is in supportive of the economic sustainability of the aquaculture

sector in Vihiga County since sustainable aquaculture practices (economic sustainability) aim to create employment opportunities for the entire society.

The respondents were also asked to indicate whether they had ever attended in training regarding aquaculture provided to fish farmers by the county government of Vihiga under the directorate of fisheries and sustainability of the service offered by the department. According to the survey, 88.5% of the respondents had attended trainings held by the directorate of fisheries and had field extension officers visit them. Only 11.5% of the respondents had never gone to aquaculture-related training. This finding demonstrates that the vast majority of fish farmers in Vihiga have received aquaculture-related training and possess the fundamental knowledge and abilities necessary for the sustainable growth of the aquaculture industry in the area. A huge percentage of the 43 respondents (55.1%) also indicated that training and extension was significantly crucial for the long-term sustainability of fresh water aquaculture. Training and extension are essential in sustainable development of aquaculture for the world to realize its optimum production by 2030 (FAO, 2018).

In addition, the respondents were asked to identify any alternative sources they used outside the Department of Fisheries' fisheries extension personnel to acquire more aquaculture skills.

In accordance with the study, the majority of fish farmers (37%) explored Facebook and the internet for additional information regarding aquaculture. Additional data was obtained from 25.6% of the respondents from sources they described as other fish producers, NGOs like Farm Africa, field days, and customer feedback. However, 15.4% and 21.8%, respectively, of the respondents indicated they acquired more about aquaculture through news stories and county government publications and local Radio programmes.

4.0. Results discussion:

The discussion of the findings of the study is presented based on the objectives of the study and research question.

4.1. Production & ecological factors' influence on the sustainability of freshwater aquaculture.

According to the research, 41% of respondents had completed secondary school. This implies that the majority of fish farmers in Vihiga are literate and have the fundamentals required to carry out aquaculture operations in the optimum manner. According to study, 16 farmers had three or more ponds, while 55 respondents owned at least two ponds (1-2 ponds). The productivity of a fish farm is heavily influenced by the number of ponds a fish farmer maintains. The fact that numerous farmers have two ponds or more is evidence that fish farming in Vihiga County is sustainable. This validates Carballo's (2008) argument that pond size and volume were controlled by the species' culture, size, and maturity.

Additionally, the survey revealed that in Vihiga, 76.9% of respondents exclusively stocked Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fish species. This is commensurate with Mbugua (2008) observation that Tilapia is the most valuable fish species cultivated in Kenya. The market value of this fish species and the availability of fingerlings for stocking were the two main determining factors. Although only a few farmers raise cat fish, they are used to prevent prolific breeding in tilapia ponds with mixed-sex culture. 3.8% of the respondents, based on the findings, had only stocked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). Thus according Mbugua (2008), African cat fish (*Clarias gariepinus*) are a less commonly grown fish species in Kenya due to a limited market. The analysis revealed that Tilapia is the predominantly cultivated species and the most sustainable for aquaculture, based on farmers' perceptions of the sustainability of cultured fish species. This is confirmed by the findings,

which showed that 53.8% of respondents thought the species under farmed was sustainable. 29.5% of respondents believed it is highly sustainable, Tilapia is the best and sustainable species to enhance production in Vihiga County.

In terms of where fish farmers obtained their fingerlings for stocking, the majority (47.3%) and 44.9%, respectively, originated from nearby farms and government farms. This indicates that government farms and other farmers' farms are the most reliable source of fingerlings for fish farmers in Vihiga. Concerning the reliability and sustainability of the source of their fingerlings for aquaculture production, 89.7% of respondents who were farmers expressed this view.

According to Oladebo, (2004) sustainability is defined as a consistent and reliable supply of However, sustainability at this level is continuing to grow fingerlings while using resources that are still available without exhausting them completely.

According to the study, 98.7% of respondents had earthen fish ponds, while only 1.3% had lined fish ponds. Earthen ponds were chosen because of the topography (28.1%) and soil quality (60.3%), respectively. The conclusion ultimately suggests that soil type, topography, capital, and water amount are the main determinants of the type of pond. This corresponds to Carballo's (2008) study, which recommended that sites for fish farming should be located where there is sufficient water supply and that sites with gravity-fed water supplies should be preferred.

Also, good soil quality is linked with the topography. Based on these findings, soil factor, topography, and water amount should be considered for the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture.

In accordance with the research, the majority of respondents (61.5%) use rivers as their primary source of water for their farmed fish. Similarly, 28.2% of the respondents stated they primarily used spring water for their fish farm. This indicates that the primary water sources for fish farming in Vihiga County are rivers and springs. Farmers should site their ponds beside springs and rivers so that they have a steady source of water for the aquaculture production.

Sustainability in aquaculture production is defined as the presence of a dependable source of water for fish farming (Mbugua, 2008). With so many rivers in Vihiga County, water is essential for fish farming, which is thought to be sustainable in the region.

From the study, the majority of respondents—92.3%—agreed that the sources of water employed in their farms were sustainable for the development of the aquaculture industry. This finding was based on farmer views about the sustainability of source water used for fish farming. This is a blatant case of how the vihiga county fresh water aquaculture can be expanded sustainably by relying solely on rivers and springs as the supply of water for aquaculture ponds. Since the region is supplied by many rivers, the water source is uninterrupted and, thus, sustainable for the practice of aquaculture.

The sustainability of fresh water aquaculture depends on maintaining the pond's water level and monitoring water quality indicators. As a result, the study revealed that the majority (42.3%) of respondents maintained the level of water in their ponds on a daily basis. While 34.6% of respondents regularly checked the water levels in the ponds. The productivity of fish ponds is improved by careful pond water level control. Sustainability improves when a pond's productivity rises. This is in accordance with Chaudhuri's (2008) review, who concluded that acclimatization and water quality management should be applied to increase the biological productivity of aquaculture. To create fish feeds more easily, one needs to understand fish nutrition for better aquaculture husbandry (Carballo, 2008).

In order to improve water quality, the water level of the ponds should be maintained daily for the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture. The research revealed that the majority of respondents (51.3%) monitored the water quality of the pond on a daily basis. These parameters comprised dissolved oxygen level, turbidity, water temperature, and phytoplankton level. A frequent monitoring of water quality parameters is necessary for fish farming's sustainability and increasing output (Shuttle, 2009).

Diseases and fish predators are problems in aquaculture operations. Based on these factors, the survey found that the majority (67.9%) of respondents thought that birds were the primary fish predators, followed by snakes (24.4%).

In order for fresh water aquaculture to better and improve, all predators should be eliminated from the fish farm. Bird scary devices should be deployed to keep them at bay. The plurality (46.2%) of respondents stated that they had never experienced fish diseases and other fish problems in their fish farm, according to the results regarding fish diseases in the farm. However, bacterial infections (29.6%) and fungal infections (11.5%) were reported by respondents. Considering that there are no significant disease issues in the area, fish disease has little impact on the growth of aquaculture in Vihiga County.

Another concern that has an effect on the aquaculture production is water contamination. Following the study, the majority of participants (42.3%) encountered a problem with water pollution spurred about by undigested feeds, pesticides, and herbicides (26.9%). Water pollution should be vastly reduced for aquaculture to develop sustainably and to prevent fish anoxia (Helfrich, 2009). In aquaculture, the utilization of fish feed is fundamental to enhancing fish pond productivity. Based on this aspect, the study's findings revealed that the majority of respondents (82.1%) feed their pond fish on commercial fish feeds. It is because commercial feeds are readily available and fairly priced in the local market. Merely 9% of respondents, however, said that they rely on organically fertilized ponds. According to Miles & Chapman (2015), fish's growth rate and feed conversion ratio (FCR) are determined by the quality of the feed used in aquaculture.

According to farmers' perceptions on the sustainability of feed, when farmers can easily access feed that is sustainable. Nevertheless, in terms of sustainability standards, feed that can yield good net weight without depleting other resources is regarded as sustainable. The latest findings on the sustainability of fish feed usage indicated that the majority of respondents—87.2%—agreed that the fish feed they are using is sustainable in the growth of fresh water aquaculture. This indicates that commercial fish feeds are preferred for the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture in Vihiga County, Kenya.

4.2. Influence of socioeconomic factors, training, and Extension services on the long-term sustainability of fresh water aquaculture

The most important asset for every commercial activity is capital. According to the study, 51.3% of respondents employed their own savings to pay for their aquaculture operations. 41.5% among those surveyed obtained the government's assistance as a result of the economic stimulus package (ESP). This indicates that the primary sources of funding for establishing and maintaining a fish farming enterprise in Vihiga County are personal savings and government assistance provided through ESP. Adu (2005) reviewed that the production culture method used has a significant impact on the amount of funding required for an aquaculture setup. There should be enough money to invest in fish farming in order for it to be economically feasible.

The funding is regarded as reliable because the finding shows that personal savings are a significant source of funds for aquaculture. The study indicates that 64.1% of respondents used family land for aquaculture operations in Vihiga County, reflecting a system of land tenure and ownership. This is validated by a review conducted by the Asian Development Bank in 2005, which found that 69% of small-scale fish farmers raised fish on land that belonged to their families (Dye, 2000). Fish production has shown to be sustainable using this method. The majority of respondents (62.8%) responded that the land tenure is sustainable to a very high extent in the growth of aquaculture when asked about the sustainability of the land tenure. This demonstrates the level of land tenure and ownership sustainability on the sustained growth of fresh water aquaculture in Vihiga County.

Based on the results of a study on the primary labor markets for aquaculture activities, 75.6% of respondents employed staff to work on their fish farms. And only 24.4% of respondents said their fish farmer used family labour. As per farmers' ideas on the sustainability of labour, using employed labour for aquaculture production is much more sustainable than relying on family members to provide labour. By giving Kenyans job chances to engage in aquaculture, this supports the sector's economic feasibility. Aquaculture shouldn't be allowed to incur extra costs because it is a risky industry. This is confirmed by Pillay (1994), who explored the fact that aquaculture is perceived as a high-risk venture compared to other types of agriculture especially when good Best aquaculture management practices are not adhered to.

Aquaculture training and extension programmes can offer crucial technical details about the industry's sustainable development (Oladebo, 2004). According to the study, 88.5% of respondents have participated in training sessions offered on by the county government of Vihiga and the department of fisheries. Only 11.5% of those surveyed had never gone to aquaculture-related training. This is in line with a research by Falusi (1991) that focused at the agriculture as center of rural development strategy, in which stronger extension services, the proper technology, and adequate market mechanisms raise rural residents' standards of life. Additionally, skilled farmers have been shown to increase fish pond productivity (Adu, 2005).

The analysis indicate that 55.1% of participants indicated training and extension are essential to very great extent, closely by 38.5% who said to great extent, in order to enhance sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture.

Agbam (2000) acknowledged that adequate extension services are required for improved production and sustainability in fish farming, and this supports his findings. In addition to government offices and trainings, farmers can obtain further information about extension and training from other sources. According to the study, 46.2% of respondents, in the majority, use social media to learn more about best practices in aquaculture management. And 37.2% of people receive their information from other sources, specifically from other farmers who have successful fish farms.

5.0. Conclusion of the study.

From the study, the following conclusions can be derived.

First of all, Vihiga County depends on fresh water aquaculture as a source of employment, nutrition, and revenue. The majority of family members have embraced the fish farming industry, which has contributed to secure its viability by seeing lesser ponds being shut down. This happens because social and economic factors have an impact on productivity, such as the availability of capital, land tenure, training opportunities, and extension services provided to farmers. There are also many rivers in the area, which are an important source of water for fish farming. This makes the area suitable for projects that involve the sustainable development of freshwater aquaculture.

Second, since there is a high demand for tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the local market, most fish farmers in Vihiga exclusively raise catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) in order to limit the overstock of tilapia in their ponds. Tilapia is the most

popular fish species cultivated in Vihiga County, the study's results indicated. The species has been regarded as sustainable in the region's development of freshwater aquaculture.

Thirdly, the findings suggest that farmers should periodically have accessibility to training and extension services. Since the county government of vihiga and department of fisheries has greatly influenced the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture through training and extension services offered to fish farmers. The majority of fish farmers seemed to have taken training on basic aquaculture practices, which has fuelled their passion in the industry. Fish farmers have been motivated by training to produce high-quality fish that may fetch high prices in the local market.

6.0. Recommendations of the study.

1. The county of Vihiga and national governments should develop an initiative through the department of fisheries to guarantee fish farmers at the sub county and ward levels in each county in Kenya have access to high quality fingerlings, quality fish feeds, and best fish farming management practices, free training on aquaculture systems, and good fish husbandry. This will promote Kenya's aquaculture's sustainable development
2. Similar to the agricultural sector, the government could offer subsidized fish farming inputs such as fish feeds, water quality parameter test kits, fertilizers, Pond limes, water pipes, and pond liners through the ministry of agriculture, livestock, and fisheries development, Kenya fisheries service and County government . In order to attract and lure more fish farmers into fish farming operations in Kenya,
3. The County Government of Vihiga should develop a clear fish marketing strategy through the department of fisheries and link with Kenya fish marketing authority so that fish farmers may readily sell their catch after harvest. As a consequence, large-scale freshwater fish farmers will be incentivized to expand the number of ponds they currently have from 1-2 to several ponds. Fish farmers will feel safer and establish aquaculture ventures if there is a clear, ready market for their products, which will encourage the growth of fresh water aquaculture in Vihiga County and throughout Kenya.
4. Fish farmers should be encouraged to form cooperatives and cluster groups for their sector so they may exchange knowledge and best management practices for aquaculture. This will promote Kenya's sustainable development of freshwater aquaculture.
5. In order to develop a diversity of fish species that can be cultivated according to the region, the government should set up a fisheries research facility in every county in Kenya. Additionally, it should be possible to do research on potential fish diseases and treatments for those that might develop in fish farms. Currently, only Kisumu, Nairobi, Sagana, and Mombasa in Kenya are home to marine fisheries research institutes.

7.0. Proposed areas of further research.

Suggested areas of further research are:

1. A study to find out why fish farming production can't meet demand for fish in Kenya, despite the country's high potential for fish farming.
2. There should also be research into the reasons why young people in Kenya are reluctant to start fish farms especially in in Vihiga County.
3. A study to investigate potential factors that influence the sustainable development of fresh water aquaculture beyond the Vihiga County in Kenya
4. There should also be research on the obstacles that aquaculture in Kenya faces as well as the factors that determine effective fresh water fish farming.

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9.0. Conflicts of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest among all the above authors. This manuscript examines different elements that affect the sustainable development of fresh water Aquaculture in Kenya. I declare that this manuscript is original and has not been published before. It is not currently being considered for publication elsewhere. No financial support was received for this study. As the only author, and my guides being co-authors I have approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of this work. And there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

10. Data Availability:

The authors shall avail data when only required and on request because of confidentiality of the data.

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